

SOIL O-LIVE

SOIL BIODIVERSITY AND FUNCTIONALITY
OF MEDITERRANEAN OLIVE GROVES

D1.1

Farms Location

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Deliverable 1.1 Farms Location

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Executive Summary

This document presents a comprehensive overview of the Soil O-live selected farms identification codes and the basic descriptors used as selection criteria. These criteria are aligned with the project's overall objective. Each farm form is accompanied by a link associated with the .kmz file that allows the geolocation of each orchard.

1. Introduction

The selection of the farms is one of the most important tasks of this project. To perform this selection a number of descriptors were gathered for all farms pre-selected. Based on this data, 52 farms were selected.

In the next section, these selected orchards are classified with a name and ID. In addition, some basic information is included in these descriptions together with a link associated with the .kmz file which allows the geolocation of each orchard.

To develop these characterization and selection tasks, the assistance from different partners of the project was needed:

- Spain: University of Jaén
- Italy: Università Degli Studi Di Palermo
- Greece: Elgo–Dimitra, University of the Aegean, Hellenic Mediterranean University
- Morocco: Ecole Nationale D'agriculture De Meknes
- Portugal: Universidade De Tras-Os-Montes E Alto Douro

2. Farm identification codes and basic descriptors of selected orchards

- 1.1. LAS CAÑADAS (ES)
- 1.2. LA CAPILLA (ES)
- 1.3. RACIONEROS (ES)
- 1.4. FINCA LA TORRE(ES)
- 1.5. FINCA LAS ERILLAS(ES)
- 1.6. EL VALLE(ES)
- 1.7. TAZAPLATA (ES)
- 1.8. EL EMPALME(ES)
- 1.9. LOS ROBLEDOS(ES)
- 1.10. FRESNUELO (ES)
- 1.11. LAS PARRAS(ES)
- 1.12. CAZORLA-LAS VENTAS (ES)
- 1.13. OLEOAGRO S.L. (ES)
- 1.14. PORTOCARRERO (ES)
- 1.15. PECHO DEL MOLINO (ES)
- 1.16. SANTA MARGHERITA_1 (IT)
- 1.17. SANTA MARGHERITA_2 (IT)
- 1.18. SEGGIO-TORRE (IT)
- 1.19. CANALLOTO (IT)
- 1.20. BRESCIANA_1 (IT)
- 1.21. IANNOTA (IT)

- 1.22. IANNOTA (ES)**
- 1.23. DOMAINE AMRI (MR)**
- 1.24. SODEOM (MR)**
- 1.25. LES VERGES DE TIZGUIT (MR)**
- 1.26. AZILAL AIT TALEB (MR)**
- 1.27. AZILAL AIT ICHOU (MR)**
- 1.28. YABEL AGRI(MR)**
- 1.29. MARKZEN (MR)**
- 1.30. ADAMOPOULOS 1 (GR)**
- 1.31. ADAMOPOULOS 2 (GR)**
- 1.32. LILEAS (GR)**
- 1.33. DRAINA (GR)**
- 1.34. STERNA (GR)**
- 1.35. KALAMITSI(GR)**
- 1.36. NITSA (GR)**
- 1.37. KIRIA (GR)**
- 1.38. PASPALAS (GR)**
- 1.39. BRIANI (GR)**
- 1.40. LA DEHESILLA (ES)**
- 1.41. UJEIRA (PT)**
- 1.42. AZINHA COVA (PT)**
- 1.43. PALIOMANDRES (GR)**
- 1.44. PLAKOYRES (GR)**
- 1.45. MANDRES (GR)**
- 1.46. AYGERINOS 1 (GR)**
- 1.47. AYGERINOS 2 (GR)**
- 1.48. OLIVART (IT)**
- 1.49. SANTISSIMA ANNUNAZIATA (IT)**
- 1.50. BRESCIANA-2 (IT)**
- 1.51. OLIVADOURO (PT)**
- 1.52. HERDADE DOS PATOS (PT)**
- 1.53. HERDADE QUINTA DA CHAMINE (PT)**

1.1. LAS CAÑADAS

ID: ES-TD1

Latitude: 38.102230

Longitude: -3.226946

Elevation: 520 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 11.72

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 102 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 90 (ha)

Age: 20 yr

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: COMPANYY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.2. LA CAPILLA

ID: ES-HD2

Latitude: 37.198283

Longitude: -4.543868

Elevation: 491 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 3-12%

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 200-400 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 70 (ha)

Age: 7 yr.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: ARBEQUINA

Owner: FAMILIY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.3. RACIONEROS

ID: ES-HD3

Latitude: 37.938880

Longitude: -3.628920

Elevation: 275 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 3-13%

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 200-400 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 163.84 (ha)

Age: 2.5 yr.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: SIKITITA

Owner: COMPANYY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.4. FINCA LA TORRE

ID: ES-ORG4

Latitude: 37.022076

Longitude: -4.694021

Elevation: 447 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 12

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 100 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 227.26 (ha)

Age: 22 yr.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: HOJIBLANCA

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.5. FINCA LAS ERILLAS

ID: ES-TD5

Latitude: 38.290469

Longitude: -3.051543

Elevation: 640 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 16.5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 100 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 7.83 (ha)

Age: 40 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.6. EL VALLE

ID: ES-ORG6

Latitude: 37.799704

Longitude: -4.310439

Elevation: 351 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 15.49

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 125 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 3.39 (ha)

Age: 25 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.7. TAZAPLATA

ID: ES-TD7

Latitude: 38.181922

Longitude: -3.032490

Elevation: 661 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 13

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 100 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 1.093 (ha)

Age: 100 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.8. EL EMPALME

ID: ES-HD8

Latitude: 38.166739

Longitude: -3.151171

Elevation: 489 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 19.7

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 200-400 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 88.59 (ha)

Age: 150 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL & ARBEQUINA

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILE](#)

1.9. LOS ROBLEDOS

ID: ES-TD9

Latitude: 38.175204

Longitude: -3.190069

Elevation: 595 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 18.05

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 100 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 32.33 (ha)

Age: 80 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ FILES](#)

1.10. FRESNUELO

ID: ES-HD10

Latitude: 38.175204

Longitude: -3.190069

Elevation: 595 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 18.05

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 100 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 32.33 (ha)

Age: 1

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.11. LAS PARRAS

ID: ES-ORG11

Latitude: 37,500081

Longitude: -4,494209

Elevation: 407 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 4.7

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 180 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 5.67 (ha)

Age: 25 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: PICUAL

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.12. CAZORLA-LAS VENTAS

ID: ES-ORG12

Latitude: 37,468361

Longitude: -4,293635

Elevation: 563 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 13.1

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 100 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 2.97 (ha)

Age: 125 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: PICUDO

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.13. OLEOAGRO S.L.

ID: ES-ORG13

Latitude: 37,474408

Longitude: -4,400291

Elevation: 812 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 19

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 80 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 8 (ha)

Age: 120 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: HOJIBLANCA-ARDUO

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.14. PORTOCARRERO

ID: ES-ORG14

Latitude: 37.487133

Longitude: -4.549456

Elevation: 352 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 4.3

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 50 (olive tree/ha)

Size: 45.74 (ha)

Age: 100 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: HOJIBLANCA

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.15. PECHO DEL MOLINO

ID: ES-TD15

Latitude: 37,410023

Longitude: -4,315411

Elevation: 587

slope (%): 13,1

Type: **TRADITIONAL**

Density of plantation: **100**

Size: **5.32**

Age: **100**

Phytochemicals last four years: **YES**

Cultivar: **HOJIBLANCA**

Owner: **FAMILY**

Gender: **MALE**

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.16. SANTA MARGHERITA_1

ID: IT-TD16

Latitude: 37.696100

Longitude: 13.047958

Elevation: 225 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 156

Size: 0.45 (ha)

Age: 25 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: Nocellara del Belice

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.17. SANTA MARGHERITA_2

ID: IT-ORG17

Latitude: 37.697400

Longitude: 13.046204

Elevation: 234 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 8

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 124

Size: 0.54 (ha)

Age: 25 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: Nocellara del Belice

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.18. SEGGIO-TORRE

ID: IT-ORG18

Latitude: 37.674132

Longitude: 12.863868

Elevation: 180 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 1.5

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 230

Size: 9.4

Age: 7

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: Nocellara del Belice

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.19. CANALLOTO

ID: IT-ORG19

Latitude: 37.633240

Longitude: 12.784877

Elevation: 76 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.8

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 155

Size: 14.50

Age: 50

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: Nocellara del Belice

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.20. BRESCIANA_1

ID: IT-TD20

Latitude: 37.596044

Longitude: 12.785091

Elevation: 32 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 14.50

Age: 50

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: Nocellara del Belice

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.21. IANNOTA

ID: IT-TD21

Latitude: 41.4418

Longitude: 13.2273

Elevation: 157 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 35%

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 2

Size: 11.37

Age: 11

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: ITRANA

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.22. VALDELOMAR

ID: ES-HD22

Latitude: 37.533343

Longitude: -4.510599

Elevation: 561 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 24.8

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 21.53

Age: 30

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: HOJIBLANCA

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.23. DOMAINE AMRI

ID: MR-ORG23

Latitude: 34.13604043

Longitude: -5.451288615

Elevation: 300 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.1

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 100

Size: 30

Age: 55

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: PICHOLINE MAROCAINE

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.24. SODEOM

ID: MR-TD24

Latitude: 33.799126

Longitude: -5.694922

Elevation: 598 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 3

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 204

Size: 55

Age: 45

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICHOLINE MAROCAINE

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.25. LES VERGES DE TIZGUIT

ID: MR-HD25

Latitude: 33.830279

Longitude: -5.26534

Elevation: 736 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.1

Type: INTENSIVE

Density of plantation: 1250

Size: 20

Age: 12

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: ARBEQUINA

Owner: COMPANYY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.26. AZILAL AIT TALEB

ID: MR-TD26

Latitude: 32.147157

Longitude: -6.649693

Elevation: 911 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.15

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 100

Size: 1.67

Age: 30

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: PICHOLINE MAROCAINE

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.27. AZILAL AIT ICHOU

ID: MR-TD27

Latitude: 32.135470

Longitude: -6.646194

Elevation: 855 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.1

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 102

Size: 9.38

Age: 11

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: PICHOLINE MAROCAINE

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.28. YABEL AGRI

ID: MR-HD28

Latitude: 33.8018341

Longitude: -5.390895

Elevation: 700 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 3

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 1000

Size: 45

Age: 13

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: Picholine marocaine, Haouzia Menara, Arbequine, Picholine Languedoc, Koronéïki.

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.29. MARKZEN

ID: MR-TD29

Latitude: 32.435078

Longitude: -6.746425

Elevation: 412 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 1

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 100

Size: 10

Age: 60

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: PICHOLINE MAROCAINE.

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.30. ADAMOPOULOS 1

ID: GR-TD30

Latitude: 37.090800

Longitude: 21.871000

Elevation: 213 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 1.3

Age: 70

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KORONEKI.

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.31. ADAMOPOULOS 2

ID: GR-TD31

Latitude: 37.0991

Longitude: 21.8533

Elevation: 310 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 5

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 1.3

Age: 70

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KORONEKI.

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.32. LILEAS

ID: GR-ORG32

Latitude: 37.0399

Longitude: 21.9478

Elevation: 90 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 180

Size: 1.1

Age: 10-150

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: KORONEKI.

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.33. DRAINA

ID: GR-ORG33

Latitude: 37.1091

Longitude: 21.8626

Elevation: 290 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 15

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 150

Size: 1.3

Age: 10-300

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: KORONEKI.

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.34. STERNA

ID: GR-ORG34

Latitude: 37.0777

Longitude: 21.8803

Elevation: 203 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 10

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 170

Size: 0.55

Age: 40

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: KORONEKI.

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.35. KALAMITSI

ID: GR-TD35

Latitude: 39.059462

Longitude: 26.459437

Elevation: 97 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 18

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 175

Size: 0.4

Age: 100

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KOLOVI

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ.](#)

1.36. NITSA

ID: GR-TD36

Latitude: 39.041719

Longitude: 26.438174

Elevation: 216 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 5.6

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 266

Size: 1.2

Age: 70

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KOLOVI, ADRAMITINI (6,5%), LADOLIA (6%), KORONEIKI (2,5%)

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.37. KIRIA

ID: GR-TD37

Latitude: 39.045899

Longitude: 26.484357

Elevation: 21 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 2.8

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 160

Size: 0.25

Age: 100

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KOLOVI

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.38. PASPALAS

ID: GR-ORG38

Latitude: 39.196995

Longitude: 26.399422

Elevation: 293 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 265

Size: 16.5

Age: 15-100

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: ADRAMITINI (80%), KOLOVI (20%)

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.39. BRIANI

ID: GR-ORG39

Latitude: 38.994362

Longitude: 26.466073

Elevation: 342 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 260

Size: 1.5

Age: 100

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: ARBEQUINA

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.40. LA DEHESILLA

ID: ES-HD40

Latitude: 37.482586

Longitude: -4.845900

Elevation: 191 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 12.6

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 295

Size: 10.25 (ha)

Age: 15-25

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KOLOVI

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.41. UJEIRA

ID: PT-TD41

Latitude: 41.530990

Longitude: -7.047058

Elevation: 527 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 8.8

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 278

Size: 2.1 (ha)

Age: 30

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: COBRANÇOSA

Owner: COMPANYY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.42. AZINHA COVA

ID: PT-ORG42

Latitude: 41.332929

Longitude: -7.041956

Elevation: 242 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 1

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 225

Size: 5.9 (ha)

Age: 20-25 yrs

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: COBRANÇOSA/ NEGRINHA de FREIXO

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.43. PALIOMANDRES

ID: GR-HD43

Latitude: 35.007795

Longitude: 24.802058

Elevation: 97 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0

Type: INTENSIVE (HIGH DENSITY)

Density of plantation: 200-400

Size: 1 (ha)

Age: 4 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KORONEIKI

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.44. PLAKOYRES

ID: GR-TD44

Latitude: 35.031905

Longitude: 24.809219

Elevation: 74 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0-5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 0.4 (ha)

Age: 40 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KORONEIKI

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.45. MANDRES

ID: GR-ORG45

Latitude: 35.068506

Longitude: 24.9009067

Elevation: 265 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 5-10

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 150

Size: 2 (ha)

Age: 60 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: KORONEIKI/THROUBOLIA

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.46. AYGERINOS 1

ID: GR-TD46

Latitude: 35.036042

Longitude: 24.851192

Elevation: 50 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0-5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 1.5 (ha)

Age: 40 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KORONEIKI

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.47. AYGERINOS 2

ID: GR-ORG47

Latitude: 35,035931

Longitude: 24,848050

Elevation: 48 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 0.5 (ha)

Age: 40 yrs.

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: KORONEIKI

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.48. OLIVART

ID: IT-ORG48

Latitude: 43.719978

Longitude: 11.308405

Elevation: 189 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 13

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 200

Size: 6.82 (ha)

Age: 35

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: FRANTOIO

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.49. SANTISSIMA ANNUNAZIATA

ID: IT-ORG49

Latitude: 43.098423

Longitude: 10.567179

Elevation: 89 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 8.5

Type: ORGANIC

Density of plantation: 160

Size: 40

Age: 80

Phytochemicals last four years: NO

Cultivar: FRANTOIO

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.50 BRESCIANA-2

ID: IT-TD50

Latitude: 37.597140

Longitude: 12.784350

Elevation: 34 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 0.5

Type: TRADITIONAL

Density of plantation: 150

Size: 2.65 (ha)

Age: 50

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: Nocellara del Belice

Owner: FAMILY

Gender: FEMALE

[LINK TO KMZ.](#)

1.51 OLIVADOURO

ID: PT-HD51

Latitude: 41.241682

Longitude: -7.102741

Elevation: 130 m.a.s.l

slope (%): 2

Type: HIGH DENSITY

Density of plantation: 800

Size: 43 ha

Age: 10

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: Arbequina

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.52 HERDADE DOS PATOS

ID: PT-HD52

Latitude: 38,155277

Longitude: -8,066218

Elevation: 114

slope (%): 1.5

Type: INTENSIVE

Density of plantation: 800

Size: 155 ha

Age: 10

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: Arbequina

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

1.53 HERDADE QUINTA DA CHAMINE

ID: PT-HD53

Latitude: 38,030429

Longitude: -8,11385

Elevation: 120

slope (%): 0.5

Type: INTENSIVE

Density of plantation: 800

Size: 130 ha

Age: 10

Phytochemicals last four years: YES

Cultivar: Arbequina

Owner: COMPANY

Gender: MALE

[LINK TO KMZ](#)

3. Soil O-live orchards map

SOIL O-LIVE ORCHARDS SELECTION

